

**When the choice of the Lagrangian, generating the curves
defining an object, also determines its topology.**

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Abstract

We review the different interpretations of the solution established by K. Schwarzschild in 1916. Regarding the exterior solution, we show that if we identify the Lagrangian with the bilinear form solution, we obtain the black hole model, homotopic to $\mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^3$. If we identify it with the square root of the bilinear form, then we obtain the wormhole, as a two-sheet covering of a manifold with boundary. If we replace this structure in the geometric framework of the Janus cosmological model, where the two sheets are linked by PT symmetry, then we obtain a finite transit time, with mass inversion upon passing the throat sphere. If we take the critical limit of the interior geometry described by Schwarzschild, where a value at the center, if not infinite, at least very high, can oppose the force of gravity, we then obtain a self-stable object presenting a gravitational redshift effect such that the ratio of the wavelengths, maximum and minimum, is then 3, which accounts for the observational data of the hypermassive objects M87* and SgrA*.

Keywords: Lagrangian, topology, Schwarzschild solution, wormhole, black hole, two folds cover of a manifold with a boundary, contractile space, throat sphere, Birkhoff theorem, PT-symmetry, mass inversion, hypermassive objects, quasars

1. Let's start with a 2-dimensional example

Consider objects \mathcal{O}_2 , defined in a two-dimensional space (r, φ) by a Lagrangian deriving from a bilinear form :

$$G\left(r, \varphi, \frac{dr}{dp}, \frac{d\varphi}{dp}\right) \quad (1)$$

With $r \in \mathbb{R}_+ = [0, +\infty]$ and such that G does not depend on φ . Considering that φ is an angle we can represent these points in a space (x_1, x_2) With :

$$x_1 = r \cos\varphi \quad (2)$$

$$x_2 = r \sin\varphi \quad (3)$$

In doing so, we identify all the points of coordinates (r, φ) and $(r, \varphi + 2k\pi)$ where k is a positive integer. This means that the object has $O(2)$ symmetry. In doing so, the space

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(x_1, x_2) is homotopic to \mathbb{R}^2 .

We will consider an object \mathcal{O}_2 whose points lie on the solution curve of a variational problem deriving from the Lagrangian $L(r, \dot{r}, \varphi, \dot{\varphi})$.

2. Choice of the Lagrangian which gives an object \mathcal{O}_2 homotopic to \mathbb{R}^2

We consider the Lagrangian:

$$(4) L = G = \frac{\dot{r}^2}{1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}} + r^2 \dot{\varphi}^2 \quad (4)$$

With action:

$$(5) J = \int L(r, \dot{r}, \varphi, \dot{\varphi}) ds \quad (5)$$

The curves resulting from Lagrange's equations correspond to the differential equation:

$$(6) \frac{d\varphi}{dr} = \pm \frac{h}{r^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{(1 - \frac{\alpha}{r})(1 - \frac{h^2}{r^2})}} \quad (6)$$

From its solutions, with for example $\alpha = 1$, we obtain several types of curves:

FIG. 1. The object \mathcal{O}_2 homotopic to \mathbb{R}^2

We have represented the circle of radius $r = \alpha = 1$. Depending on the value of the parameter h , we obtain three sets of curves, completely different. For $0 < |h| < 1$ we have spiral curves (b). For $0 < |h| < 1$ the drift dr/d becomes zero at $r = \alpha = 1$. For $|h| \geq 1$, these are curves that spiral indefinitely towards the center $r = 0$. The direction of the winding depends on the sign of h .

For any value of r , we can integrate by varying the angle φ from 0 to 2π and thus obtain a quantity $2\pi r$, which can be set to zero at the geometric center. Our object \mathcal{O}_2 is contractible. We see that, starting with an object \mathcal{O}_2 , defined by this bilinear form, we discover an underlying topological property. As we have just defined it, our object \mathcal{O}_2 is homotopic to \mathbb{R}^2 .

A mathematical geometer, living in this two-dimensional space, decides to associate two ways of measuring lengths with it. Let us call this bilinear form G :

$$G\left(\frac{dr}{dp}, \frac{d\varphi}{dp}\right) = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}} \left(\frac{dr}{dp}\right)^2 + r^2 \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dp}\right)^2 = G\left(\frac{dx_i}{dp}\right) \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (7)$$

He then introduces these two real lengths:

- One refers to the curves drawn "outside" the sphere of radius α , that is, for $r > \alpha$:

$$s_{ext} = \int \sqrt{G} ds \quad (8)$$

- The other refers to the "interior" of this sphere, that is to say $0 < r < \alpha$:

$$s_{int} = \int \sqrt{-G} ds \quad (9)$$

In doing so, our mathematician geometer believes he has explored all the properties of this object \mathcal{O}_2 , defined by its bilinear form.

3. Choice of Lagrangian leading to a nearly object \mathcal{O}_2 non contractible

Let's opt for the Lagrangian:

$$L' = \sqrt{G} = \sqrt{\frac{\dot{r}^2}{1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}} + r^2 \dot{\varphi}^2} \quad (10)$$

The action becomes:

$$J' = \int L'(r, \dot{r}, \varphi, \dot{\varphi}) ds = \int L^{1/2} ds \quad (11)$$

The variation gives:

$$\delta J' = \int \delta(L^{1/2}) ds = \int \frac{1}{2\sqrt{L}} \delta L ds = 0 \quad (12)$$

We obtain the same Lagrange equations. But our new choice of Lagrangian prevents us from drawing curves for $r < \alpha$.

The (actual) length is defined only for $r > \alpha$:

$$s_{ext} = \int \sqrt{G} ds \quad (13)$$

The object \mathcal{O}_2 is no longer contractible. The closed curves drawn on it have a perimeter limited to $2\pi\alpha \neq 0$.

3.1. Interpretation as a manifold with a boundary

First idea: we can consider that this object \mathcal{O}_2 is a manifold M_2 bordered by the circle of perimeter 2π . The curves $\varphi = \text{constant}$ are interrupted on this circle. Same definition for the real length, on the two sheets.

FIG. 2. \mathcal{O}_2 as a manifold with boundary

We have represented by a gray area what does not belong to the object \mathcal{O}_2 , assimilated to a manifold with a boundary.

3.2. Interpretation as a two-layer covering of a manifold with a boundary

We can consider another option, allowing to avoid this interruption of these radial geodesics by considering this time that the object \mathcal{O}_2 is the two-sheet covering of our manifold with boundary. Same definition of the length, real.

FIG. 3. \mathcal{O}_2 as a two-layer coating of a bordered manifold

Thus, by giving ourselves a bilinear form, according to our topological assumptions, we have arrived at three different structures for this object.

- Homotopic to \mathbb{R}^2 ,
- M_2 manifold with a boundary,
- Two-sheet covering of a M_2 manifold with a boundary.

Assuming that an observer inhabits one of the two sheets of \mathcal{O}_2 and is located at a point M , they would deduce that there exists a second point M' of \mathcal{O} , located on the other sheet, with the same set of two coordinates r and φ . At the connecting point between branches (c) and (d), there is a presumption of discontinuity at $r = \alpha$. Knowing that the choice of

coordinates remains arbitrary, our inhabitant of \mathcal{O} can, for example, opt for the change of variable:

$$r = \alpha(1 + L_n ch\rho) \quad (14)$$

Which transforms its bilinear form into:

$$\frac{th^2\rho}{L_n ch\rho} dr^2 + \alpha^2(1 + L_n ch\rho)^2 d\varphi^2 \quad (15)$$

The border then corresponds to the value $\rho = 0$. The two sheets of \mathcal{O}_2 then correspond, respectively, to $\rho > 0$ and to $\rho < 0$. A limited development in the neighborhood of shows that the suspected non-regularity at this point disappears. The observer concludes that the object \mathcal{O} , where he lives, is regular.

3.3. The object \mathcal{O}_2 , as a subset of the space \mathbb{R}^3 in which it is embedded

An inhabitant of a 3D space, in this case Euclidean, the space An inhabitant of a 3D space, in this case Euclidean, the space \mathbb{R}^3 then considers that this object \mathbb{R}^3 is immerseable in its own world \mathbb{R}^3 , which is not systematically possible. To do this, it adds a z coordinate by considering that the equation of the meridian is given by:

$$dr^2 + dz^2 = \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}} \quad (16)$$

Which gives the meridian curve:

$$z = \pm 2\sqrt{\alpha(r - \alpha)} \quad (17)$$

This is the surface generated by the rotation of a lying parabola, rotating around its axis, a Flamm surface (FIG.4). This allows us to consider that curves (c) and (d) are each inscribed on one of the two sheets joined according to a throat circle.

FIG. 4. The object \mathcal{O}_2 imbedded in \mathbb{R}^3

4. A geometric object \mathcal{O}_4 as a solution to Einstein's equation

This object \mathcal{O}_4 lies in a $\mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^3$ space. The coordinates are (t, x, y, z) with $t \in \mathbb{R}_+$ and $(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3$.

4.1. \mathcal{O}_4 as defined by Schwarzschild

Schwarzschild considers the bilinear form:

$$g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu \quad (18)$$

And Lagrangian :

$$L(x_i, \dot{x}_i) = \sqrt{g_{\mu\nu} \dot{x}_\mu \dot{x}_\nu} \quad (19)$$

This will require him to define the object only in a portion of space where this Lagrangian is positive, which he also identifies with the real length, which he explicitly defines by:

$$ds = \sqrt{g_{\mu\nu} dx_\mu dx_\nu} \quad (20)$$

And :

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx_\mu dx_\nu \quad (21)$$

This bilinear form then becomes the metric of the object. The action being:

$$J = \int L (x_i , \dot{x}_i) dp = \int \sum_{\mu, \nu} \sqrt{g_{\mu\nu} \frac{dx_\mu}{dp} \frac{dx_\nu}{dp}} dp \quad (22)$$

The basis for his construction of curves, which for it are then curves of minimal length s , geodesics of the object \mathcal{O}_4 .

It imposes on its bilinear form that its coefficients $g_{\mu\nu}$ be independent of time, which amounts to saying that the four-dimensional geometric object \mathcal{O}_4 results from the translation, along the time coordinate t , of a three-dimensional geometric object \mathcal{O}_3 . This object is not invariant by T-symmetry, changing t to $-t$.

Second hypothesis: the geometric object has spherical symmetry. It is then logical to move to a spherical coordinate system.

$$(t, x, y, z) \rightarrow (t, r, \theta, \varphi) \quad (23)$$

With :

$$r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \geq 0 \quad (24)$$

$$x = r \sin\varphi \cos\theta \quad (25)$$

$$y = r \sin\varphi \sin\theta \quad (26)$$

$$z = r \cos\theta \quad (27)$$

Taking into account stationarity and spherical symmetry this leads to the form

$$H(r) \dot{t}^2 - F(r) \dot{r}^2 - G(r) (\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2\theta \dot{\varphi}^2) \quad (28)$$

Then Schwarzschild, by introducing an integration constant α , which he chooses to be positive (“Schwarzschild radius”), presents this solution using an intermediate variable “*hilfsroße*”:

$$R = (r^3 + \alpha^3)^{1/3} \geq \alpha \quad (29)$$

His solution is in two parts, limited by the value of the variable $R = R_a$ (surface of the star creating the field). For $R > R_a$, that is, ”outside the mass”, in a vacuum, its bilinear form, a solution to Einstein’s equation, without right-hand side (and are respectively the Ricci tensor and the Ricci scalar), is written:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (30)$$

And the bilinear solution form is :

$$G_{ext} \left(t, R, \theta, \varphi, \dot{t}, \dot{R}, \dot{\theta}, \dot{\varphi} \right) = \left(1 - \frac{R}{\alpha} \right) \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{R}{\alpha}} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2 \right) \quad (31)$$

It is defined positive, due to the nature of this variable $R > \alpha$. To account for observational data (advance of Mercury's perihelion) Schwarzschild is led to give its integration constant the form:

$$\alpha = \frac{2 G M}{c^2} = \frac{8 \pi G \rho R_a^3}{3 c^2} \quad (32)$$

or $R < R_a$ "inside" this sphere filled with an incompressible fluid of constant density ρ , its bilinear form is a solution to the Einstein equation with second member:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} = 0 = \chi R_{\mu\nu} \quad (33)$$

By introducing a second characteristic length:

$$\hat{R} = \sqrt{\frac{3 c^2}{8 \pi G \rho}} \quad (34)$$

The form, for $R > R_a$ is:

$$G_{int} = \left[\frac{3}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{R_a^2}{\hat{R}^2}} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{R^2}{\hat{R}^2}} \right]^2 c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{R^2}{\hat{R}^2}} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2 \right) \quad (35)$$

Inside this object the length s , real, is always defined by (the metric):

$$ds = \sqrt{g_{\mu\nu} dx_\mu dx_\nu} \quad (36)$$

The continuity of the two forms is ensured on the sphere $R = R_a$, as is the continuity of the curves arising from the Lagrangian $L = \sqrt{G}$ (which are then geodesic curves, along which a length s is real). In calculations, in mixed notation, Einstein's equation is written:

$$R_\mu^\nu - \frac{1}{2} R \delta_\mu^\nu = \chi T_\mu^\nu \quad (37)$$

By assimilating the contents of the sphere of radius R_a to a perfect fluid, the tensor is written;

$$T_\mu^\nu = \begin{pmatrix} \rho c^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -p \end{pmatrix} \quad (38)$$

The equation thus translates the fact that the geometry is determined by the energy content, the pressure also being an energy density (kinetics of thermal agitation) per unit of volume:

$$p = \frac{\rho \langle v^2 \rangle}{3} \quad (39)$$

In the course of his calculations Schwarzschild obtains a pressure p which, inside the mass, from a zero value at the surface, increases according to the equation :

$$p = \rho c^2 \left[\left(\frac{2}{3 \cos \chi_a - \cos \chi} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (40)$$

The position, inside the mass being defined by the angle χ according to:

$$R = R_a \sin \chi \quad (41)$$

So this pressure becomes :

$$p = \rho c^2 \left[\left(\frac{1}{\frac{3}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{R_a^2}{R^2}} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{R^2}{R_a^2}}} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (42)$$

It is zero at $R = R_a$, at the surface of the object, and maximum at $R = 0$, at the center:

$$p_{max} = \rho c^2 \left[\left(\frac{1}{\frac{3}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{R_a^2}{R^2}} - \frac{1}{2}} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (43)$$

Of course, under the physical conditions envisaged by Schwarzschild (stars like the Sun) this pressure remains moderate, as an energy density per unit volume, compared to the term ρc^2 . This means that the speed of thermal agitation is low compared to the speed of light:

$$\langle v \rangle \ll c \quad (44)$$

But it considers the case where the maximum pressure p_{max} tends towards infinity, when:

$$R_a = \sqrt{\frac{8}{9}} \hat{R} = 0.9428 \hat{R} \quad (45)$$

For a star of density ρ , let us define the reference mass:

$$M = \frac{4}{3} \pi \hat{R}^3 \rho \quad (46)$$

The pressure will become infinite for a critical mass:

$$M_{crit \ phys} = 0.838M \quad (47)$$

When the mass of an object (neutron star) is such that the pressure within it is no longer negligible compared to ρc^2 , its contents can be compared to a plasma where the pressure becomes the radiation pressure:

$$p_r = \frac{\rho c^2}{3} \quad (48)$$

For today's physicists, this speed of light is limited to :

$$c_0 = 300,000 \text{ km/s} \quad (49)$$

Under these conditions, the conditions mentioned by Schwarzschild, corresponding to a maximum pressure greater than :

$$p_{r0} = \frac{\rho c_0^2}{3} \quad (50)$$

Physicists consider this to be outside the scope of physics. But Schwarzschild attributes this increase in pressure to a variation in the speed of light, corresponding to the law :

$$c = c_0 \sqrt{\frac{\frac{3}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{R_a^2}{\hat{R}^2}} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{R^2}{\hat{R}^2}}}{\frac{3}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{R_a^2}{\hat{R}^2}} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{R^2}{\hat{R}^2}} - 1}} \quad (51)$$

He is therefore the first to have considered that the speed of light could vary, within mass, when certain conditions are reached. We will then note that we have no measurement invalidating this possibility, the measurements of c only referring to empty regions. This question, with the answers immediately provided by the specialists concerned¹, was only considered very late². Extract from the basic work "Gravitation", here are these curve:

¹Gravitation Wheeler , Thorne et Misner [1]

²Because the Karl Scharzschild's second paper, describing the geometry inside the mass, was only available in English in 1999.

FIG. 5. The evolution of the pressure inside the mass, according to [1]

What interests us is the topology of the object \mathcal{O}_4 . Its geometry was carefully analyzed in 1916 by Ludwig Flamm [2]. It is conceived as the connection between two manifolds connected according to their common edge: the surface of the star. The invariance with respect to time (by time translation) means that this \mathcal{O}_4 can be assimilated to the translation according to the time coordinate of a hypersurface \mathcal{O} . This object \mathcal{O} corresponds to the union, according to a sphere S , of a portion of sphere S , of radius of curvature \hat{R} and of a Flamm hypersurface F_3 . By making a cut of this object according to $\theta = \pi/2$, Flamm obtains a Surface F_2 , of revolution, defined by the metric:

$$ds^2 = \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}} \quad (52)$$

He then realizes that this object can be immersed in \mathbb{R}^3 , by adding a third coordinate z and writing:

$$dr^2 + dz^2 = \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}} \quad (53)$$

Which gives the meridian curve :

$$z = \pm 2\sqrt{\alpha(r - \alpha)} \quad (54)$$

And the object, to which we will give its name, in Figure 4. Overall, the meridian of this object is given by Flamm [2]:

FIG. 6. The meridian of the surface of Flamm F_2 [2]

The object is contractile, as is which is homotopic to $\mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^3$.

4.2. David Hilbert's interpretation (1916)

In 1915 and then 1916 Hilbert undertook to lay the foundations of the physics of his time¹. ("Grundlagen der Physik" [3],[4]). A covariant formalism being sought, he was the first, a few days before Einstein, to publish the field equation:

$$K_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} K g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\partial \sqrt{g} L}{\partial g_{\mu\nu}} \quad (55)$$

It is effectively identical to Einstein's equation. Hilbert only denotes the Ricci tensor and its scalar by the letter K instead of R . The difference lies in the choice of the bilinear form and therefore in the interpretation of the Lorentz transformation, key to the theory of special relativity. For Einstein, there is only one real length $s = c\tau$, which he defines as proper time and which is defined by the Lorentz metric:

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu = c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 \quad (56)$$

The coefficients of its bilinear form are not all of the same sign and

¹Where a global description was merged the two known forces: the force of gravity and the electromagnetic force.

$$\det(g_{\mu\nu}) < 0 \quad (57)$$

To Hilbert :

$$\det(g_{\mu\nu}) > 0 \quad (58)$$

Hilbert's universe is therefore quasi-Euclidean, which he expresses with the relation:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \delta_{\mu\nu} + \epsilon h_{\mu\nu} \quad (59)$$

Hilbert only includes in the second version of his memoir the version of the bilinear form referring to a portion of the empty universe. He says nothing about this second solution, describing the geometry inside the mass. Perhaps because this construction is associated with geodesics that cannot be compared with observations. Regarding the determination of trajectories, he bases it, in spherical symmetry, on the bilinear form:

$$F\dot{R}^2 + R^2(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2\theta\dot{\varphi}^2) + H\dot{l}^2 \quad (60)$$

The fact that he identifies the coefficient of the term $(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2\theta\dot{\varphi}^2)$ with R^2 (which seems to simplify the calculations) means that R automatically identifies with the intermediate Schwarzschild quantity. And he writes his result, his form with its Euclidean signature :

$$G\left(x^i, \frac{dx^i}{dp}\right) = \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}} + R^2(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2\theta\dot{\varphi}^2) + \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}\right)\dot{l}^2 \quad (61)$$

He then shows a difference in signs between the different coefficients by posing:

$$l = i t \quad (62)$$

Which gives :

$$G\left(x^i, \frac{dx^i}{dp}\right) = \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}} + R^2(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2\theta\dot{\varphi}^2) - \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}\right)\dot{t}^2 \quad (63)$$

In doing so, Hilbert adopts Henri Poincaré's interpretation of special relativity, according to which the universe is Euclidean, but where the fourth coordinate, time, is purely imaginary. His action is:

$$J = \int G\left(x^i, \frac{dx^i}{dp}\right) dp \quad (64)$$

Therefore, for him, there is no constraint on R , which he identifies with a "radial variable": $R \in \mathbb{R}_+$. The topology of his contractile object \mathcal{O}_4 is therefore $\mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^3$. He notes the possible existence of a singular region at $r = \alpha$, which will later turn out not to be a true singularity, but a coordinate singularity. He then introduces three types of solution curves, arising from the variation of the action, for which he defines, as already mentioned above in 2D, three possible (real) lengths:

- When $G > 0$ it defines the length of a "segment" $\lambda = \int \sqrt{G \left(\frac{dx_i}{dp} \right)} dp$
- When $G < 0$ it is the length on a "time line" $\tau = \int \sqrt{-G \left(\frac{dx_i}{dp} \right)} dp$

The quantity τ is then the proper time.

- When $G \left(\frac{dx_i}{dp} \right) = 0$. These are trajectories of zero length, which he called "null lines", followed by photons.

4.3. The modern interpretation of \mathcal{O}_4

For objects exempt from criticality, stars, including neutron stars, the geometric interpretation is that defined by Schwarzschild. The object is contractile and therefore, in this case, has the topology $\mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^3$.

However, progress in stellar dynamics has led theorists to consider the evolution of stars with a mass greater than 8 solar masses into supernovae. The star then collapses onto its iron core. This undergoes inelastic compression, with the energy being dissipated in the form of a neutrino flux. What remains instead is an object made up of tightly packed neutrons. But it is then considered that the mass exceeds what we will call a geometric critical mass. For a given density ρ when this critical (geometric) mass is:

$$M_{crit\ geom} = \frac{4}{3}\pi \hat{R}^3 \rho \quad (65)$$

The radius of the corresponding object is:

$$R_a = R_{crit\ geom} = R_s = \frac{2 G M}{c^2} = \hat{R} = \frac{3 c^2}{8 \pi G \rho} \quad (66)$$

The meridian of the object becomes :

FIG. 7. Meridian of object \mathcal{O}_3 in a geometric criticality

That is to say when $\chi_a = \pi/2$. The point with coordinate $R = 0$ is then a true singularity, which a change of coordinates cannot eliminate, in the sense that the value of the Kretschmann scalar is zero at this point.

He specifies his action M and N being functions of what he considers R (henceforth designated by the letter r^1) as a "radial variable". This is a point that we want to emphasize strongly because, if he starts from the hypothesis that the construction of solution-objects represents the set of solution-curves and comes from the particular choice of the Lagrangian, from the bilinear-solution form, his choice, hereafter, then leads to a contractile object and to an imposed topology $\mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^3$. A choice that will then become standard² by constituting the modern interpretation of the Schwarzschild exterior solution as "an extension to the whole of space-time".

erste Schritt hierzu ist die Aufstellung der Differentialgleichungen der geodätischen Linien durch Variation des Integrals

$$\int \left(M \left(\frac{dr}{dp} \right)^2 + r^2 \left(\frac{d\vartheta}{dp} \right)^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \vartheta \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dp} \right)^2 + W \left(\frac{dl}{dp} \right)^2 \right) dp.$$

Wir erhalten als Lagrangesche Gleichungen diese:

FIG. 8. Hilbert's Action and Spacetime Lagrangian[4]

¹Which becomes different from the authentic radial variable presented by Schwarzschild according to

$$r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \in \mathbb{R}$$

²See S. Chandrasekhar : The Mathematical Theory of Black Holes [5]

Lagrange's equations immediately provide, for radial trajectories, the free fall time of a witness mass falling on the Schwarzschild sphere, or the escape time from this sphere:

$$\Delta t \cong -\frac{1}{c} \log(r - 2M) \leftarrow \infty \quad (67)$$

FIG. 9. Coordinate time t and proper time [5]

On the other hand, if we assimilate the magnitude s to the proper time experienced by an observer accompanying this witness mass in its fall from a point corresponding to the value $R = R_0$ of the coordinate, R to the point $R = 0$ (then identified as the center of the object, insofar as, like Hilbert, they identify R as "a radial coordinate") it comes:

$$\Delta \tau = \frac{1}{c} \frac{2}{3\sqrt{2M}} R_0^{3/2} \quad (68)$$

If we consider that we are trying to describe an imploding object, this collapse occurs in a finite time, located in days, for stars whose masses are measured in solar masses, which, on the time scale used in astrophysics, is extremely brief. As it then becomes logical to identify the coordinate t with the proper time experienced by a distant observer, this configuration encourages Oppenheimer and Snyder, in 1939 [6] to propose that this stationary solution of the Einstein equation without a right-hand side can describe the rapid implosion of an object which, for an external observer, lasts an infinite time.

This is the birth certificate of the black hole model

Nothing can then escape from this object or cross a horizon sphere. For an external observer, the object will exhibit an infinite gravitational redshift effect.

Since the trajectories are a priori derived from this Lagrangian $L = G$, spacetime is contractile and always has the topology $\mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^3$. Because of this choice, it then becomes possible to construct the trajectories in what is considered the interior of the black hole.

FIG. 7b. Various classes of time-like geodesics described by a test particle with $E^2 > 1$: (a), (b), (c): orbits of the first and the second kind with eccentricity $e = 3/2$ and latera recta, 4.5, 2.5, and 1.94 respectively ($M = 3/14$ in the scale along the coordinate axes); (d), (e): unbound orbits with $l = 1$ and with imaginary eccentricities $e = 0.001i$ and $0.1i$ ($M = 0.3$ in the scale along the coordinate axes).

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FIG. 10. Trajectories of objects plunging into the black hole [5]

4.4. Permutation of space and time coordinates in black holes

Theorists then adopt the two definitions of (real) lengths proposed by the mathematician David Hilbert. For radial trajectories:

When $R > R_s$

$$\tau^{ext} = \frac{1}{c} \int \sqrt{G} dp \quad (69)$$

When $R < R_s$

$$\tau^{int} = \frac{1}{c} \int \sqrt{-G} d \quad (70)$$

A problem then arises: the inversion of the signature inside the black hole. But cosmologists propose a solution, now accepted by the entire scientific community:

Inside the black hole, the space and time coordinates swap roles

$$R \rightleftharpoons t$$

4.5. The wormhole model

If we opt for the Lagrangian:

$$L = \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{1}{R_s}} - R^2 (\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2)} \quad (71)$$

The trajectories resulting from the Lagrange equations corresponding to $R < R_s$ cannot be considered real. If we exclude the geometric solution of the boundary manifold type, we are then led to consider its two-sheet covering. This space-time is no longer contractible. This structure, called a wormhole, represents a passage which is supposed to connect either two distinct regions of space-time, or a region of our space-time and a "parallel" space-time.

FIG. 11. Wormhole, Kruskal 1960 [7]

In both cases, we can isolate the spatial part of the solution and then, by making cuts as Flamm did in 1916, obtain the meridian of the object, this time with a complete parabola.

FIG. 12. Wormhole Meridian

The transit time, in the time linked to the witness mass, is then finite and brief, in one direction as in the other. But for an outside observer, this operation will seem to last an infinite time.

4.6. Birkhoff's uniqueness theorem [8, 9]. Traversable Wormholes

When we limit ourselves to a topology $\mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^3$, arising from the Lagrangian of FIG 8, it is then logical to require a uniqueness of the solution. This excludes the presence of crossed terms in the bilinear form. The solution then has the symmetry T: it is invariant when changing t to $-t$. We then no longer speak of a stationary solution, but of a static solution. On the other hand, in the case of the wormhole this constraint is no longer imperative. We can then consider the bilinear form :

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{1}{R_s}} \pm A \dot{R} \dot{t} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2\right) \quad (72)$$

And the Lagrangian:

$$L = \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{1}{R_s}} \pm A \dot{R} \dot{t} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2\right)} \quad (73)$$

This can be obtained at the cost of a simple change of time coordinate, introduced by A. Eddington in 1924 [10]. By designating by t_S the ‘‘Schwarzschild time’’, without cross term, and by t_E the Eddington time, we pass from one to the other by the change of variable :

$$t_S = t_E \pm \frac{1}{R_s} L_n \left(\frac{R}{R_s} - 1 \right) \quad (74)$$

The Lagrangian then becomes:

$$L = \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{1}{R_s}} \pm \frac{2 R_s c}{R} \dot{R} \dot{t} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2\right)} \quad (75)$$

We can then consider that the object \mathcal{O}_4 results from the union of two varieties according to their common edge, the throat sphere, of area $4 \pi R_s^2$, by assigning this crossed term a plus sign and the other a minus sign. For example in this combination of the two objects:

$$L_1 = \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{1}{R_s}} - \frac{2 R_s c}{R} \dot{R} \dot{t} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2\right)} \quad (76)$$

$$L_2 = \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{1}{R_s}} + \frac{2 R_s c}{R} \dot{R} \dot{t} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2\right)} \quad (77)$$

This gives a finite transit time from the first sheet to the second, and an infinite one in the other direction: a traversable wormhole [11]. The opposite situation is achieved by reversing the signs. With such a model, the implosion of a supernova's iron core, instead of producing a "central singularity," results in the mass being sent into a parallel universe. Another way to view the phenomenon is to consider a single bilinear form, with the time coordinate reversed on the other sheet:

$$L^{(+)} = \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^{(+)^2} - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{1}{R_s}} - \frac{2 R_s c}{R} \dot{R} \dot{t}^{(+)} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2\right)} \quad (78)$$

$$L^{(-)} = \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^{(-)^2} - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{1}{R_s}} - \frac{2 R_s c}{R} \dot{R} \dot{t}^{(-)} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2\right)} \quad (79)$$

With :

$$t^{(-)} = -t^{(+)} \quad (80)$$

If we refer to [12] this inversion of the time coordinate is synonymous with the inversion of energy and mass. Taking this into account we are led to write, t being the time of an observer located in the positive sheet:

$$L^{(+)} = \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 - \frac{1}{R_s}} - \frac{2 R_s c}{R} \dot{R} \dot{t} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2\right)} \quad (81)$$

$$L^{(-)} = \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{1}{R_s}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \frac{\dot{R}^2}{1 + \frac{1}{R_s}} + \frac{2 R_s c}{R} \dot{R} \dot{t} - R^2 \left(\dot{\theta}^2 + \sin^2 \theta \dot{\varphi}^2\right)} \quad (82)$$

The (geodesic) trajectories resulting from the Lagrangian $L^{(-)}$ then evoke a repulsion. But we will then note that the second sheet of our object is no longer embeddable in \mathbb{R}^3 . Indeed, the attempted embedding leads us to the differential equation:

$$dz^2 = -\frac{r}{r + R_s} dR^2 \quad (83)$$

It has no real solution: surfaces defined by shapes and Lagrangians are not automatically embeddable in a higher-dimensional space. It should be noted in passing [11] that crossing the throat also results in a P-symmetry:

FIG. 13. P-symmetry at the crossing of the throat sphere [11]

The two sheets are then PT-symmetric. If we consider them as the two-sheet covering of an M_4 manifold we then have the Janus Cosmological Model [13].

4.7. Back to the surge in pressure at the center of the star

In the above, the progressive compression of the mass modifies the meridian, which passes from the configuration of FIG 6 to that of FIG 13 with a geometric criticality. But, if we then follow the solution developed by K. Schwarzschild in February 1916 [14] an intermediate configuration occurs with the following meridian where the angle reaches 71° :

FIG. 14. Physical criticality

This image is for illustrative purposes only. Near the center, a small portion of space is shown where the time coordinate (and mass) are reversed. A 2D didactic image can be given by considering two structures, one being a blunt cone, representing a portion of space with constant positive curvature (spherical cap) surrounded by a portion without

FIG. 15. Educational image of mass inversion at the center of the object

FIG. 16. Evolution of the time factor beyond criticality

curvature (truncated cone), together which can be called a "posicone", the other being a "conjugate" portion, a "negacone", where a structure without curvature surrounds a portion with constant negative curvature (horse saddle), FIG 15.

We will analyze this scenario by extending the time factor for a mass value exceeding the critical mass, see FIG 16.

We see in FIG 17 a small volume developing near the center where the mass is reversed. The diameter of this singular region increases very quickly: parabolically as a function of the excess matter.

FIG. 17. Parabolic growth of the radius of the throat sphere

If the inverted mass remains in place, the diameter of this singular region tends towards the geometric critical radius, the Schwarzschild radius. Several scenarios can then be considered.

- "Soft" version: the excess matter remains negligible compared to the mass of the star. This would be the case for a subcritical neutron star absorbing the stellar wind of a companion star. The latter would be very quickly expelled from the star, partly because the very strong pressure forces would tend to disperse it, and partly because it would be subject to the field, repulsive to this inverted mass, created by the mass of the star. The name plugstars is suggested for such objects.
- A first "hard" version: a merger of two subcritical neutron stars. The total mass would then be twice the critical mass. The violent opening of the central singularity, comparable to that of a camera's aperture, is accompanied by a very significant mass inversion, generating a powerful gravitational wave. The signal received by devices such as LIGO and Virgo, interpreted as a "black hole merger," will then lead to an overestimation of the masses.
- Finally, a scenario should be considered where the inverted mass exceeds, in absolute value, the residual positive mass. It would not disperse and would remain in place. The self-attracting positive mass could then envelop an object that has become invisible

FIG. 18. Images of hypermassive objects M87* [15] and SgrA* [16]

to an observer of the same mass. This residual positive mass, no longer supplied with energy by fusion reactions, would see its temperature drop to the temperature of the CMB: $2.7^\circ K$. One might wonder whether certain nebulae, called proplyds, similar to gaseous environments surrounding protostars, and with a relatively low temperature, might not correspond to such formations. In fact, it is difficult to understand why, surrounding a protostar at $2000^\circ K$, they would not take on the same temperature.

4.8. Comparison with observation

When we consider the "soft" version, where the subcritical object is a plugstar, the surge in core pressure to a value that is, if not infinite, at least very high, counterbalances the force of gravity. Observationally, we have a gravitational redshift $z_{gr} = 2$, which gives a ratio of 3 between the maximum and minimum wavelength values (or "equivalent temperatures").

This is what emerges from the analysis of the two images of the supermassive objects M87*[15] and SgrA*[16], see FIG 18.

FIG. 19. Hoag galaxy ([17, 18])

4.9. On the nature of such objects and quasar phenomenon

For these two objects to be "giant black holes," a mass of gas would have to be located in the foreground, which would explain why their central part is not perfectly black. But, since these two objects are very different in terms of their mass and temperature, this interpretation seems unlikely. In any case, the M87* object, equipped with two jets, is a genuine quasar. It is suggested that these objects are the result of the focusing, at the center of galaxies, of centripetal density waves, as mentioned for the Hoag galaxy.

Observational data concerning this annular formation of a rotational movement of the order of 250km/s , but by a radial velocity. But this bright ring is a density wave and we must not confuse the propagation speed of the wave and the speed of the gas in which the wave propagates. This measured rotation speed is that of the gas, in which a circular density wave propagates radially. As in spiral waves these waves result in a recompression of the gas, generating young stars, the width of the wave simply reflects the time that elapses between the birth of young stars and the moment when they cease to excite the gas by UV emission, typically between 5 and 20 million years. The width of the wave of the Hoag galaxy being 7.4kpc this gives a radial velocity of the wave of 730 to 1470km/s . It would then reach the center of the galaxy in a time between thirteen and fifty million years. Since the magnetic Reynolds number is large compared to unity, the wave then gathers the lines of force of the pre-existing magnetic field in the galaxy, which is estimated at one microgauss. By gathering these lines, an intense dipole magnetic field is formed.

FIG. 20. Diagram of the formation of a quasar [19]

In classical modeling, energy emission is associated with an accretion phenomenon. In the proposed scheme, the centripetal wave, comparable to a gaseous tsunami, by gathering at the center of the galaxy, would cause a rise in density and temperature such that Lawson conditions are reached in a large mass, this phenomenon being accompanied by an enormous production of energy, released in the form of plasma emitted along two lobes. The magnetic field gradient then transforming these jets into immense particle accelerators gives them energies of the order of those of the cosmic rays, of which they are the source. The outstanding question is that of the origin of these circular density waves. We conjecture that they reflect irregularities in the cosmic expansion, due to joint fluctuations of the metrics, which we undertake to model within the framework of the Janus model. The result is that the confining force of galaxies, exerted by the negative mass, would prove to be more important in regions where the expansion speed would weaken, which would be the case in Seyfert galaxies [20], which lead to a value of the Hubble constant of $70 \pm 5 \text{ km/s/Mpc}$,

lower than the standard value: $70 \pm 1 \text{ km/s/Mpc}$ We conjecture, although this study has not been done, that the value of the Hubble constant attached to irregular galaxies would then be lower, reflecting a relaxation of the confinement.

5. Conclusion

When we look at the various theoretical publications that make up the discipline of cosmology, we see an evolution. Before the Second World War, authors unambiguously defined their framework for researching and interpreting solutions to Einstein's equation. They defined an element of length $ds = \sqrt{g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu}$. This element, constructed on the basis of real coordinates, is therefore essentially positive or zero. In 1915-1916, the presentation by mathematician David Hilbert presented the problem in a completely different way. For him, the solutions to the field equation, those that he and Einstein have just published, are quasi-Euclidean bilinear forms that he denotes $G\left(x^i, \frac{dx^i}{dp}\right)$ or $g_{\mu\nu} = h_{\mu\nu} + \varepsilon \gamma_{\mu\nu}$. If we translate this in terms of signature, this form corresponds to the Euclidean signature $(+++)$. He then takes up the interpretation proposed in 1902 by the mathematician Henri Poincaré, that is to say that the time coordinate is pure imaginary: $x_4 = i t$. The signature of the form then becomes $(+++)$. This can be considered as the origin of the modern formulation, and of its change of signature, for example in the modern formulation of the Lorentz metric $ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2$ which makes that the proper time is then no longer the length s , but corresponds to its definition according to Hilbert, that is $\tau = \int \sqrt{-G} dp$. The Hilbert action is then $J = \int G dp$ and we will note that the variation calculus leads to the same equations as with the Schwarzschild action $J = \int \sqrt{g_{\mu\nu} \dot{x}^\mu \dot{x}^\nu} dp$, but without the constraints imposed by its result (real proper time if $R > \alpha$).

We have thus shown that the topology of the object differs depending on the definition of the action, starting with a 2D example, which is easy to grasp. After the Second World War, it was clear that those who called themselves cosmologists opted without exception for Hilbert's choice, the example cited being Chandrasekhar's work "Mathematics of Black Holes", the hypersurface solutions being then homotopic to $\mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^3$. This corresponds to the analytical extension carried out by Kruskal in 1960 "thanks to which the solution was

extended to the whole of space-time”.

Birkhoff’s uniqueness theorem then prohibits the presence of an n crossed term in $dr dt$ in the metric. This is then interpreted by saying that this metric must be not only stationary, that is, invariant under time translation, but also static, that is, invariant under changing t to $-t$.

But by opting for Schwarzschild’s choice, the hypersurface becomes the two-sheet covering of manifold with a boundary, with the Schwarzschild sphere preceding a throat sphere. If we stick to a static metric, without a cross term, the transit time through this structure, connecting two Minkowski spaces, occurs in a finite time, in both directions, in proper time, but remains infinite if evaluated with the time coordinate t . But the two-sheet covering structure allows for the presence of a term in $dr dt$. Under these conditions, it is possible to construct a wormhole allowing passage in only one direction. If we opt for the Janus Cosmological model, the two sheets are linked by a T-symmetry, and any mass crossing the throat is inverted. We then return to the internal geometry defined by Schwarzschild in 1916 and to the critical structure he described. Any input of matter then causes the time factor to reverse near the geometric center, resulting in the expulsion from the object of an amount of matter equivalent to this excess mass. It is suggested that the hypermassive objects located at the centers of the M87 galaxies and the Milky Way are such self-stable objects. It is found that the gravitational redshift effect they generate fits perfectly with the ratio of the maximum and minimum wavelengths in the two objects, very close to the theoretical value: 3.

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